

THE EFFECT OF EXPERIENTIAL MARKETING ON THE PURCHASE OF MILLENNIAL GENERATION (STUDY ON CONSUMERS OF LOCALLY BREWED COFFEE SHOPS IN SEMARANG CITY)

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Abstract

This study aims to find out consumer buying actions based on experiential marketing in the free generation of coffee shop consumers in Semarang City. The population in this study is the entire generation of independent consumers who drink coffee at locally brewed coffee shops. The number of samples is 120 respondents, with the sampling technique used is accidental sampling. The research data source is primary data, with data collection techniques using questionnaires. Multiple linear regression data analysis technique. The results of the analysis using the multiple linear regression equation show that the variables sense, think, act and related variables have a positive effect on consumer buying actions, while feeling has a negative and significant effect on consumer buying actions. The results of the test for the coefficient of determination R^2 showed 84.1%. It can be concluded that the marketing experience variable can explain the variation of the consumer-purchasing variable while the remaining 15.9% of consumer buying-action is explained by other variables outside this research model. The results of the suggestion test accept the influence of sense, think, act, related variables and reject the influence of feeling variables. Results.

Keywords: Sense, Feel, Think, Act, Relate, Consumer Buying Action.

INTRODUCTION

Schwartz (2000) stated that consumer purchases are driven by emotion. According to Goleman (1999), emotion is an act of instability of thoughts, feelings, and passions, which are out of control. If this concept is applied in consumer buying actions, the buyer's emotion is an act of acceptance or rejection of the reaction of marketing activities by the company. The response can relate to anger, sadness, fear, pleasure, love, surprise, annoyance, and shame (Goleman, 1999).

Research on millennials drinking coffee in coffee shops can reveal consumer behavior (Solikatur et al., 2015). Coffee contains caffeine, which can stimulate hormones, namely cortisone and adrenaline; as a result, coffee eliminates drowsiness, increases mental awareness, mind focus, keeps the body awake, and increases energy. Drinking coffee in a shop provides a consumer experience (experiential marketing), especially for the free generation consuming coffee, which includes sensing, feeling; thinking; acting; and relating as Schmitt (1999) states that millennials have the habit of drinking locally brewed coffee as part of their lifestyle and expresses freedom by visiting coffee shops that serve manually brewed coffee.

The existence of coffee shops is closely related to culinary tourism. Culinary tourism means traveling and experiencing situations by buying special foods or drinks, trying to explore them, and tasting them to be remembered. Visiting places such as coffee shops to enjoy food and drink coffee is included in culinary tours, while the act of buying to be repeated in the future is the result of the consumer's personal experience. A coffee shop is a special place that provides coffee drink services and a place to make friends, study, meet, take photos, and do business while enjoying other menus. As for the barista, the coffee shop functions as a job role and expresses a passion. Drinking coffee can evoke positive emotions, including joy, kindness, compassion, contentment, friendship, calm, and happiness.

Nowadays, many local coffee shops have popped up because drinking coffee is among the habits of Indonesians. Therefore, the culinary business becomes quite profitable (Mustinda, 2016). Semarang coffee shops also support culinary tourism, especially local coffee shops that provide brewed coffee. The current research examines whether experiential marketing influences the buying actions of the independent generation at local concoction coffee shops in Semarang City.

According to Engel and Blackwell (2016), consumer buying action is recognizing needs, searching for information, evaluating alternatives, purchasing, and producing results. Consumers involve in determining: (1) product choice: what product to buy from a wide selection of types of products/services (2) brand choice: what brand is preferred out of the many existing brands (3) choice of agent: which agent is chosen to decide the transaction with him (4) payment time: when the product is purchased (5) method of payment: how to pay.

Kotler (2016) states that there are five stages of a person's decision process in making a purchase, namely 1) problem recognition, 2) information search, 3) alternative assessment, 4) buying action, and stage 5) post-purchase behavior.

Consumers form preferences for brands or products in the choice set in the evaluation stage. The possibility of buying the most liked product will appear. Two factors lie between purchase intention and purchase action. These factors are the attitude factors of other people and unanticipated situational factors. Figure 2 below explains the stages between evaluation and buying action.

Lee et al. (2011) stated that experiential marketing is a memory or experience that goes deep into customers' minds. According to Kartajaya (2010), experiential marketing is a marketing concept that aims to form loyal customers by touching customer emotions by creating positive experiences and feelings toward services and products. Bigham (2005) defines experiential marketing as a new approach to providing information to consumers about brands and products. Likewise, Andreani (2007) concluded that experiential marketing is an approach to providing more than just information about a product or service. Thus, experiential marketing in this study is the marketing strategy carried out by companies to create experiences for consumers, including sense, atmosphere, thought, action, and social relations.

According to Diahnisa (2017), the millennial generation, or what is referred to as Generation Y, is a group of young people born in the early 1980s to early 2000s or the demographic group after Generation X or the baby bust generation. Millennial characteristics differ by region and socio-economic conditions. However, this generation is generally characterized by increased use and familiarity with digital communications, media, and technology (Ummanah et al., 2021). Since the era of social media, it has been proven that the millennial generation drinks more coffee than previous generations (Mustinda, 2016).

Drinking coffee is not just a drink but how to drink coffee in a shop is a culture, tradition, trend, and lifestyle. He also said that the two things that caused the level of coffee consumption for the millennial generation were 1) coffee culture, which tended to increase coffee consumption. At the same time, urbanization was also a supporting factor. People who moved to cities started consuming coffee as a lifestyle trend. 2) status, experience, and personality also make up values in the millennial generation, who consider drinking coffee more stylish than other drinks.

Artisans are experts at making handicrafts (Ratu, 2020). Artisan products are made one by one by hand, so it requires a long process. They are usually using local materials and traditional techniques. The manufacturing process is more precise; therefore, the resulting product is also higher quality. They are associated with various kinds of products made by hand, such as food and beverages: bread, tea, and coffee. Artisanal coffee products mean someone's expertise in making delicious and distinctive coffee drinks.

As it has become a culture, coffee has developed into a unique commodity, where the type of origin of the coffee beans and the quality of the coffee beans are standardized. Coffee fans are familiar with and choose coffee beans from certain places, for example, coffee from coffee beans grown in Aceh, Toraja, Mandhailing, Malabar-West Java, Wamena, and coffee beans planted in the Bajawa Flores.. Their regional origin makes coffee beans unique in aroma and sense. In coffee shop services, what is meant by artisan coffee products are shops that offer single origin for buyers, while manual brew is a way of brewing coffee manually without using a machine. According to Wahyu (2016), the concept of an artisan coffee shop is unique in the coffee industry, where the process of serving and the shape of the shop are the selling points of the artisan coffee shop itself.

According to Accenture's findings (2020), there are several changes in consumer behavior that businesses need to be aware of, namely, around 56% of consumers are oriented toward local products, 61% of consumers buy environmentally friendly products, and 72% of consumers are trying to reduce consumption which causes food waste, thus making consumers more aware in purchasing something. Around 84% of consumers admit that they will continue their lifestyle for a certain period and will also encourage the growth of local artisan businesses. Local coffee as a raw material for manual brewing coffee that the millennial generation has known includes Aceh Gayo, Mandhailing, Toraja, Kintamani Bali, and Bajawa Flores coffee. When consumers are going to order it, what they mean is coffee with a single origin. Vixisfty, or French press, is the manufacturing process, while medium means that the coffee is grounded until half-coarse, not powder and not coarse (hard). What is meant by brewed coffee is a method of making coffee by stirring coffee grounds from a cup that has been poured with water. Pouring water

with a temperature below 85-90°C as much as 100-150 ml. Comparison of coffee beans with water volume 1 gram of coffee: 10 ml.

Coffee shop entrepreneurs commonly use several coffee shop designs, including minimalist shop designs, roadside shop designs, coffee house designs, and restaurant and cafe designs that blend with nature; there are parks and Instagramable spots. In essence, all shop designs must meet the desires and build consumer senses that can provide an atmosphere of intimacy, beauty, and joy.

Coffee consumption in Indonesia has increased rapidly since the 2000s (Wanda, 2023). It is predicted that this will increase as the middle class's income and lifestyle change.

Meanwhile, understanding the age of consumer demographics is essential in offering products (Kotler and Keller, 2016); therefore, marketers must understand the age of consumers as their market segments. Age differences result in differences in senses and preferences for products. The millennial generation is the age group of 20-40 years who are relatively quick to accept something new, the trend of drinking coffee in coffee shops. The millennial generation is the millennial generation that is adaptable to technology. They tend to like to use technology to facilitate all their activities. Advances in payment technology have made this generation even more cashless.

Meanwhile, the reality of the coffee shop as a lifestyle is increasingly emphasized by the need for modernization; coffee shops are now a place for social interaction and for young people to hang out. The habit of millennial generation is that they like brewed coffee in their free time and spend their money drinking coffee at coffee shops, making this activity part of their lifestyle (Solikaturun, 2015).

METHODOLOGY

Research Explanatory

The type of research used in this research is explanatory research. According to Sugiyono (2017), explanatory research is a research method that intends to explain the position of the variables of concern and the influence between one variable and another. In this study using population, samples and hypotheses. According to Indriantoro and Supomo (2014), a population is a group of people, events, or things with specific characteristics. Meanwhile, according to Sanusi (2014), the population is the entire collection of elements that show particular characteristics that can be used to make conclusions. The population in this study are consumers of the younger generation who visit coffee shops and have consumed brewed coffee in the city of Semarang. The sample is part of the total population (Sugiyono 2016). The sampling technique in this study uses a non-probability sampling technique by using a purposive sampling technique, namely a sampling technique based on specific criteria or considerations (Sugiyono, 2017). These criteria include the Act: 1) Consumers drink coffee at coffee shops, 2) aged 17-30 years, and 3) Purchase of these products for self-consumption. While the hypothesis is a conjecture or temporary statement that is used to solve a problem in research whose truth must be tested empirically.

Questionnaire Design and Data Collection

Data collection techniques in this research by using questionnaires. Sugiyono (2017) a questionnaire is a technique data collection is done by giving a set of questions or a written statement to the respondent to be answered with an answer scale of 1-5. The score starts from the numbers one to five. Score one indicates strongly disagree, score two indicates Disagree, Score three indicates quite agree, Score four indicates Agree, and score five indicates Strongly Agree. The number of respondents studied was 120 people, with a question of 22 items.

Variable measurement

Measurement of research variables determines the amount of information about the value of variables related to business problems. The measurement of the research variables is as follows in Table 1:

Table 1: Variable measurement

No	Concept Definition	Indicator	Mark
1	Consumer buying actions (Y1) are consumer actions that form tendencies to choose between several brands and can also form intentions to buy the most preferred brand (Kotler and Keller, 2016)	1. Product priority 2. Brand fame 3. Convenience of place 4. Preciseness 5. Easy payment (Kotler and Keller 2016)	Y1 Y2 Y3 Y4 Y5
2	Sense (X1), the consumer's experience when consuming, is sensory-based (Schmitt 2011)	The experience of 1. Seeing coffee 2. Hearing the coffee 3. Tasting the coffee 4. Smelling the coffee	X1.1 X1.2 X1.3 X1.4
3	Feel (X2) is a sensory impression because it is related to the emotions of a person's soul (Andreani, 2007)	1. Good vibes 2. Chill 3. Relax 4. Surprise	X2.1 X2.2 X2.3 X2.4
4	Think (X3) is a person's ability to think about an offer from a coffee shop of a product (Andreani, 2007).	1. Ideas 2. View 3. Image (Andreani, 2007)	X3.1 X3.2 X3.3
5	An act (X4) is an activity related to the whole individual to improve his life and lifestyle (Andreani, 2007).	1. Physical experience 2. Lifestyle 3. mutual influence (Andreani, 2007)	X4.1 X4.2 X4.3
6	Social relations (X5) are actions related to culture and its reference groups that can create a social identity (Andreani, 2007)	1. Cultural ties 2. Preference group 3. Habit (Andreani, 2007)	X5.1 X5.2 X5.3

Data Analysis Technique

Data analysis in this study used a multiple regression model approach. Ghazali (2017) states that in regression analysis, apart from measuring the strength of the relationship between two or more variables, it also shows the direction of the relationship (influence) between

independent variables. The form of the linear regression equation written is as follows:

$$Y = \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \beta_4 X_4 + \beta_5 X_5 + e$$

Validity and Reliability Test

The data analysis results show that all the indicators used in the variables have a value of r count greater than r table, so all indicators for each variable are valid. The results indicate that the indicators in the questionnaire can measure the variables used in the study. In the validity test of this study, all question items are valid

Based on the results of the analysis, it was found that all variables had Cronbach's Alpha values greater than 0.60, so it can be said that all measuring concepts for each variable were reliable, meaning that the questionnaire used was reliable. This also means that the answers given are consistent and are expected to be used for further research. As for the reliability test, all questions show reliable.

RESULT and DISCUSSION

The respondents in this research are consumers of coffee shops in Semarang with profiles as follows:

Respondents who visited locally brewed coffee shops in Semarang were primarily male. Seventy-nine (65.8%) and 41 (34.2%) are women. The large number of men is because men have a longer time until night, while women are bound by social norms that limit the nighttime to 21.00. This study's results align with the research of Hanafi, Martunis, and Sulaiman (2018).

Respondents who visited local concoction coffee shops in Semarang City were aged > 21-30 years, as many as 85 people (70.8%). This shows that buyers of locally brewed coffee are aged 21 and over. The reason for choosing a coffee shop is because they enjoy the coffee, the atmosphere of beauty, and the event, which is Instagramable. Judging from the age category, coffee shop visitors are the agile generation, a generation who are young at heart. This research aligns with the study of Sawitri and Yuziani (2021) and Hanafi, Martunis, and Sulaiman (2018).

Regarding the frequency of respondents' visits to coffee shops to enjoy locally brewed coffee types in the city of Semarang, 71 respondents (59.17%) visited 5-10 times in three months. This explains consumers habitually drink coffee at local concoction coffee shops.

Respondent's responses regarding Sense experience

The mean score for the Sense variable is 3.33, which means that the respondents gave a high enough response to the Sense variable. Of the three indicators used to measure the Sense variable, it can be seen that the viewing experience indicator, with an average of 3.45, is the highest indicator of the Sense variable. These results indicate that consumers decide to buy based on their experience of seeing the pleasure of drinking coffee while sitting in the coffee shop they visited. Consumers can enjoy the sense of the coffee purchased as expected, such as the desired sense from the single-origin Gayo Arabica wine flavor, which is described as having a sour Sense and aroma of a wine.

Respondent's responses regarding feel experience

The mean score for the feel variable is 3.54, meaning that the respondents responded highly to the feel variable. The four indicators used to measure feel variables show that the lazy-to-move indicator, with an average of 3.62, is the highest indicator of the feel variables. This can be interpreted as the customer's visit to the concoction coffee shop with the power of a pleasant, beautiful, warm feel becomes the experience. Consumers feel that when they sit while drinking coffee in a shop, they feel happy and happy due to the influence of coffee, which causes happy hormones and the store atmosphere in the environment around the shop.

Respondent's responses regarding think experience

The mean score for the thought variable is 3.63, meaning that the respondents responded highly to the thought variable. From the three indicators used to measure the thought variable, it can be seen that the pleasant indicator, with an average of 3.45, is the highest indicator of the thought variable. This shows that when deciding to buy, consumers perceive that coffee shops are a choice for a Senseful way of drinking coffee for the agile generation. The experience of consumers drinking coffee at a shop can generate ideas and positive thoughts about a program.

Respondent's responses regarding act experience

The result of calculating the mean value for the following variable is 3.67, which means that the respondents perceive the act highly. Of the three indicators used to measure behavior, the hip verbal indicator, with an average insect score of 3.75, is the highest perceived indicator. This means that consumers consider it essential to support their activities by drinking coffee at a coffee shop as a venue for friendship, telling stories, speaking, and being different from others. The effect of drinking coffee in a shop feels more stylish compared to other drinks, such as soda.

Respondent's responses regarding relatedness experience

The result of calculating the mean value for the social relations variable is 3.28, which means that the respondents perceive social relations as relatively high. Of the three indicators used to measure social relations, the indicator of coffee drinking habits in a shop with an index of 3.42 is the indicator that is perceived the highest by respondents. This data explains that the consumer experience of drinking coffee at a coffee shop is influenced by the habit of the millennial generation visiting shops with colleagues.

Respondent's responses regarding consumer buying action

Respondents' responses to consumer purchases have a mean value of 3.45, which means that the respondents highly perceive consumer buying behavior. Of the five indicators used to measure purchasing decision variables, the tavern fame indicator, with an average of 3.75, is the indicator that is perceived the highest by respondents. This can be said to be consumer buying action based on the observations above; consumers buy coffee in a shop because of the influence of the fame of the coffee shop.

Regression Analysis

Regression analysis, apart from measuring the strength of the relationship between two or more variables, also shows the direction of the effect between the independent variable and the dependent variable (Ghozali, 2013). Multiple linear regression analysis in this study was used to determine the impact of the variables Sense (X1), Feel (X2), Think (X3), Action (X4), and Social Relations (X5) on consumer buying actions (Y). The regression results are as follows:

$$Y = 0,261X_1 - 0,053 X_2 + 0,322X_3 + 0,114X_4 + 0,840X_5 + e$$

Hypothesis test

Hypothesis testing produces the value of t_{test} as follows:

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t-test	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1,304	,924		1,412	,161
	Sense	,261	,101	,188	2,601	,011
	Feel	-,053	,071	-,041	-,740	,461
	Think	,322	,092	,214	3,507	,001
	Act	,114	,050	,087	2,267	,025
	Related	,840	,114	,610	7,400	,000

a. Dependent Variable: Consumer buying action

1. The regression coefficient of the sense variable (b1) is 0.261, at t-test 2,601 > 1.657 and sig on alpha 0,05 %, meaning that the hearing variable has a positive effect on consumer buying behavior. These results indicate that the Sense variable directly affects consumer buying action. If the hearing variable's value increases, consumer purchases will also increase, assuming the other variables are zero or constant. These results follow the research of Chasanah, Muzammil, and Janny Rowe (2018).
2. The regression coefficient of the feel variable (b2) is -0.053, at t-test -,740 < 1.657 and not sig on alpha 0,05%, meaning that the feel variable does not affect consumer buying behavior. These results indicate that feel variables are inverse to consumer buying actions. If the provision of the atmosphere experience is improved, it does not affect consumer buying actions. These results do not follow Chasanah et al. (2018).
3. The regression coefficient of the think variable (b3) is 0.322, at t-test 3,507 > 1.657 and sig on alpha 0,05 %, meaning that the thought variable has a positive effect on consumer buying actions. These results indicate that the thought variable has a relationship that is in the same direction as the consumer's buying action. If the value of the view variable increases, then consumer purchases will also increase, assuming the other variables are zero or constant. These results follow the research of Chasanah et al. (2018)
4. The regression coefficient of the act variable (b4) is 0.114, at t-test 2,267 > 1.657 and sig on alpha 0,05 %, meaning that the Act variable has a positive effect on consumer purchases. These results indicate that the follow-up experience variable directly affects consumer buying action. If the Act variable's value increases, consumer purchases will

also increase, assuming the other variables are zero or constant. Drinking coffee at a coffee shop is a way of expressing their lifestyle for the millennial generation. These results are consistent with Chasanah et al. (2018).

- The regression coefficient of the social relations variable (b5) is 0.840, at t-test 7,400 > 1.657 and and sig on alpha 0,05 %, meaning that the social relations variable has a positive effect on consumer buying actions. These results indicate that the social relations variable is linear positive to consumer buying action. If the value of the social relations variable increases, then the consumer-purchasing action will also increase, assuming that other variables are zero or constant. In the Langgas generation, social identity often changes and is inconsistent in buying actions. These results follow the research of Chasanah et al. (2018).

Coefficient Determinant

The coefficient of determination essentially measures how far the model's ability to explain the variation in the changeability of the swing variable is as follows:

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	,921 ^a	,847	,841	1,329

Based on the results of the determination test, the coefficient of determination is obtained as seen from the Adjusted R Square of 0.841. It can be concluded that the experiential marketing variable can explain the variation in the consumer buying action variable by 84.1%, while other variables outside this research model explain 15.9%

Research Model

Experiential marketing as a marketing strategy focuses on creating an imprinted experience in the minds of consumers. This marketing strategy aims to form consumer buying actions loyal to the product or service by packaging it in the form of activities to provide an experience that can make an impression on the hearts and memories of consumers. This strategy emphasizes understanding sense, atmosphere, thought, action, and social relations as experiential marketing. The research framework model developed is shown in Figure 4:

Figure 4: Research Model

Drinking coffee at a local concoction coffee shop is also a social space for business activities, study, and friendship networks. Customers have different purposes for coming to a coffee shop, from wanting to relax to business prospects and taking photos with colleagues. There is only one similarity; customers will enjoy each of their activities at the coffee shop with delicious coffee.

Serving delicious coffee is the hope of every customer who comes; therefore, seeing the coffee shop situation and listening to customer wishes is the first step to exemplary service to customers. According to customers, the sense of good coffee and a comfortable coffee shop is the sense of sour, soft, fruity coffee with Arabica coffee types.

One of the reasons visitors can enjoy coffee at local coffee shops is because they can see how the process is made, for example, by *manual brewing*, one way to serve coffee brewed manually, but this method requires special filter paper. Another way of *manual brewing* is the *French press*. The coffee serving technique is made using special cups. If you will see the shape of a glass that has a press on the lid of the glass, then it's a tool called a *French Press*; how to brew it by letting the coffee sit for a while for approximately 4 minutes, with a dose of 60 gr for 1 liter of water. After that, press the top slowly until the coffee grounds are pressed to the bottom. After that, it is poured into a cup while still *fresh*.

The buying action of consumers drinking locally brewed coffee in coffee shops is usually influenced by the atmosphere; it has been proven that the millennial generation finds the sensation of drinking coffee different from drinking coffee at home, which is made traditionally, namely brewed coffee. Usually, brewed coffee is simply by pouring coffee into a cup, brewing it with hot water, then stirring it, wait a few moments for the coffee grounds to settle to the bottom. In contrast to drinking coffee at locally brewed coffee shops, there are practically no coffee grounds. In addition, drinking coffee in a shop makes customers feel an atmosphere outside of themselves, which can provide inspiration, enthusiasm for work, warm friendships, and even a new atmosphere. However, in this study, the atmosphere does not affect consumer buying actions. This is because customers feel a different atmosphere is not felt at the coffee shop they visited.

Consumer buying actions based on touch experience think that drinking locally brewed coffee in coffee shops is for the millennial generation because shops have an attractive service concept starting from the physical evidence (tangible), the appearance of service-responsive employees, and care to generate positive thoughts from customers to be experienced to visit again. This finding is in line with research conducted by Chasanah et al. (2018), Raissa (2013), Indriani (2006), and Franto (2018) that the thought dimension of marketing experience influences consumer buying actions.

Acceptance of the act variable hypothesis test, it can be explained that consumers decide to visit and drink locally brewed coffee at coffee shops due to the results of measuring lifestyle and the mutual influence of information on consumer experiences in the habit of drinking coffee at coffee shops. The act of buying consumers drinking locally brewed coffee in a coffee shop for the younger generation because the way of drinking coffee in a shop creates a positive

impression to improve the customer's lifestyle. They feel that coffee shops always provide good service, service, and delivery, creating a positive customer image. This finding is in line with research conducted by Chasanah et al. (2018), Raissa (2013), Indriani (2006), and Franco (2018) that the action variable influences consumer buying behavior to visit and drink locally brewed coffee at coffee shops.

The influence of negative social relations variables on consumer buying actions is due to the millennial generation's social identity, which often changes and is inconsistent in buying actions. Weaknesses in cultural ties, reference groups, and consumer habits can influence purchase behavior. This finding is not in line with research conducted by Chasanah et al. (2018), Raissa (2013), Indriani (2006), and Franto (2018).

The results of this study align with Franto's research (2018), which says that the five experiential marketing variables positively affect consumer buying decisions in the small food business consumer study, as well as the findings of Raissa (2013).

The coefficient of determination R² which is very high at 88.8%, indicates the strong influence of the variables in this study on the predicted variables. The experiential marketing variables indeed explain the change in consumer buying action. This means that for coffee shop owners studying consumer behavior in buying decisions, it can be seen from the effects of the dimensions of sense, atmosphere, thought, action, and social relations. This is for consumer behavior analysts; experiential marketing variables are good consumer buying action models because, for research using cross-sectional survey data, the coefficient of determination R² is good (Ghozali, 2017). Experiential marketing research provides scientific insights into the field of consumer behavior for actual buying actions

Millennials represent a high share of shoppers in many coffee shop industries. Due to the development of brain maturation, millennials experience strong emotional reactions. Marketers can use neuro-brain information to target the slim generation by delivering attention-grabbing messages that can impact emotional expression vividly and create new experiences in stores. The millennial generation relies more on feelings and does not thoroughly consider the consequences.

Implications For Research And Practice

The action variable is among the variables of sense, thought, action, and social relations that have the most minor influence on consumer buying actions. Therefore, coffee shop owners continue to increase efforts to strengthen the effect of reference groups, cultural ties, and customs in providing services so that they become experiential marketing in the future.

The Millennial generation comes to a coffee shop to enjoy coffee and the atmosphere, sample other menus, chat with friends, meet, and take photos. To support this, a coffee shop must have a clear concept and provide comfort and beauty.

limitations and future research

From the results of this study, researchers found the Act's limitations:

The broad coverage of independent research variables that influence consumer buying actions, and the limits of the research method approach, only a few variables cannot cover a broader range and are beyond the researcher's control.

The time to carry out the research process and research costs are relatively high, so researchers must be careful in simplifying this research.

To overcome the limitations in this research, what needs to be done for further research are:

Expanding the research object by adding the unit of the research object, Increase the number of the respondents, and the possibility of using an experimental method of research.

CONCLUSION

The findings of this research are:

Variables of Sense, thought, action, and social relations, influence consumer buying actions. As for variable Feel variables do not affect to consumer buying actions. Regression model can be developed in this research

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